

AUTOMATIC HEADLIGHT DIM / DIP

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Abstract— *The number of vehicles on our roads is burgeoning day by day. This is turn forced almost all this vehicle manufactures to think about the extra safety instruments and electronic controls to attach with these products for giving the users a safety derived in all road conditions through a mass flow traffic. If asked, one should always mention that the right driving is very cumbersome due to the dazzling light problems and the frequent dipping of headlights by manual means that often causes fatigue to the driver particularly at the time of peak traffic. So naturally to get rid of this perennial problem, an automatic mechanism has to come up to dip the headlamp automatically whenever required. For keeping a motor vehicle under perfect control and reins of the driver, different types of controls and accessories are provided in an automobile around the driver's seat, on the dashboard and at the footboard. Simply, an automatic high beam controller is a unit, which can automatically judge when the headlight beam needs to be lowered, and which dip the headlamp from which beam to a dipped beam. Our work proposes an effective automatic control of the vehicle headlamps based on the detection of head lights and tail lights under night time road conditions. This project is about to control high beam or low beam automatically.*

Keywords: *automatic high beam controller.t*

I. INTRODUCTION

The number of vehicles on our roads is burgeoning day by day. For this reason almost all the vehicle manufactures have to think about the extra safety instruments and electronic controls to attach with these products for giving the users a safety. Modern automotive vehicles include a variety of different lamps to provide illumination under different operating conditions. Headlamps are typically controlled to alternately generate low beams and high beams. Low beams provide less illumination and are used at night to illuminate the forward path when other vehicles are present. High beams provide significantly more light and are use to illuminate the vehicle's forward path when other vehicles are not

present. Daylight running lights have also begun to experience widespread acceptance. High beam are used for illuminating a road doesn't have very much traffic on it. By that way the driver can see further ahead for any road obstructions. High beam is also used when a driver is one an unfamiliar road and if there isn't much in the way of lighting such as street lamps. Automatic high beam, as explained is opposite beam detector. Another probable application of automatic high beam is our high beam response due to another high beam and automatically our high beam becoming low. Now a day there are many accidents that cause from the beam light. Our work proposes an effective automatic control of the vehicle headlamps based on the detection of head lights and tail lights under night time road conditions. This project is about to control high/low beam automatically. This project will make sure that the consumer will save their time and energy also for those who have the illness of nervous. This project will not disturbing any manual function of the beam. As well as developmental processes in a spatial or spatio-temporal context.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

TITLE: Intelligent Automatic High Beam Light Controller.

AUTHOR: Mohammed Alsumady and Shadi.

YEAR:2014

DESCRIPTION: The work in this paper focusing on an automatic high beam light controller is required to make night time driving safer and more friendly to other cars on the road. This study provides a simple, low-cost, and easy-to-implement method. The work in this paper is focusing on the design and operation of a microcontroller-based Adaptive Headlight System (AHS) for automobiles is the subject of this study. The major goal of this system is to provide a cost estimate They demonstrate a successful system for recognising cars in front of a camera-assisted vehicle The work in this paper focusing on, even when the traffic situation requires it, drivers use high lights sparingly at night. This paper focuses on developing

an automatic high beam light controller to enhance nighttime driving safety and promote better road etiquette.

III. EMPATHY

Ability to adapt and optimize lighting conditions for safety and efficiency, providing a better driving experience while minimizing glare for other road users. It emphasizes the positive impact on both the driver and those sharing the road. These intelligent systems display an understanding of the environment, adjusting light patterns to accommodate various scenarios, such as oncoming traffic or varying weather conditions. Through this, they contribute to both driver and pedestrian well-being, minimizing glare for others while ensuring optimal visibility for the driver. Embracing the empathy for autonomous headlights involves acknowledging their capacity to navigate the delicate balance between illumination and consideration, ultimately fostering a safer and more harmonious driving environment for everyone on the road.

IV. OBJECTIVE

- ❑ To develop an automatic high beam to low beam converter, you would typically start by designing a system that can detect the need to switch from high to low beams based on certain criteria, such as the presence of oncoming vehicles or streetlights.
- ❑ Once the system detects the need to switch beams, it would then need to control the vehicle's headlights accordingly. This could involve sending signals to the vehicle's headlight control system to switch between high and low beams.
- ❑ The system would also need to ensure that the transition between beams is smooth and does not cause discomfort or confusion to other drivers on the road.

V. COMPONENTS REQUIRED

- ❑ SWITCH MODE POWER SUPPLY
- ❑ ESP8266 NODE MCU
- ❑ L298N DUAL H-BRIDGE MOTOR DRIVE
- ❑ BATTERY
- ❑ LIQUID CRYSTAL DISPLAY (LCD)
- ❑ LIGHT DEPENDENT RESISTOR (LDR)

VI. BLOCK DIAGRAM

Fig.1 Block Diagram

VII. WORKING

Autonomous headlights using a Microcontroller and LDR (Light Dependent Resistor) operate by sensing ambient light conditions and adjusting the headlight intensity accordingly. The LDR serves as a sensor that changes its resistance based on the ambient light level. The LDR is connected to the Microcontroller and acts as a light sensor. As ambient light changes, the LDR's resistance alters proportionally. The Microcontroller continuously reads the resistance value from the LDR. It interprets this value to determine the ambient light level. Based on the ambient light level, the Microcontroller decides whether to activate high beams, low beams, or adjust the Intensity. For instance, in low-light conditions, it might switch to high beams for better visibility. The Microcontroller sends signals to control the headlight intensity or switch between high and low beams. The system constantly monitors light conditions, making real-time adjustments to ensure optimal visibility without causing glare for oncoming drivers. The LDR is connected to the Microcontroller, which acts as the brain of the system. The Microcontroller reads the resistance value from the LDR at regular intervals to determine the ambient light level. Based on this reading, the Microcontroller decides whether to activate high beams, low beams, or adjust the intensity of the headlights. For example, in low-light conditions, the Microcontroller might switch to high beams to improve visibility. It can also adjust the intensity of the headlights based on the ambient light level to ensure optimal visibility without causing glare for oncoming drivers. The Microcontroller sends signals to control the headlight intensity or switch between high and low beams. This system allows for real-time adjustments to lighting conditions, providing safer and more efficient nighttime driving.

VIII. TESTS AND RESULTS

IX. REFERENCE

Fig 3 Project Model

Machine Learning for Adaptive Lighting: Implement machine learning algorithms to adapt the lighting system based on user preferences and historical data.

IX. FUTURE SCOPE

Energy Consumption Monitoring: Include sensors to monitor energy consumption, providing insights into usage patterns and enabling further optimization. Expand Sensor Compatibility Investigate the integration of additional sensors for more comprehensive environmental awareness. These sensors can provide valuable data that can be used to identify patterns in energy usage, detect inefficiencies, and optimize energy consumption. For example, by monitoring energy consumption over time, the system can identify peak usage periods and suggest ways to reduce energy usage during these times. In addition to monitoring energy consumption, the system can also benefit from the integration of additional sensors for more comprehensive environmental awareness.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The development and implementation of an autonomous headlight system using a microcontroller present both technological advancements and challenges. Achieving a successful autonomous headlight system requires addressing issues related to sensor calibration, power supply stability, environmental interference, algorithmic precision, reliable communication, temperature effects, mechanical durability, integration with vehicle systems, regulatory compliance, and user interface design. Through rigorous testing, optimization, and adherence to industry standards, a well-engineered autonomous headlight system can enhance driving safety and convenience by intelligently adapting to changing lighting conditions.

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/271843873>
[Automatic High Beam Controller for Vehicles](#)